

PSYCHOLOGY AND CREATIVITY: WAYS OF INTERACTION AND INFLUENCE ON PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: The article considers aspects of the relationship between psychology and creativity, emphasises their role in understanding human nature and personality formation. It is studied how culture and artistic activity influence human mental organisation and value orientations. Special attention is paid to the psychology of art, which studies the processes of perception and creation of works, as well as their influence on emotional and cognitive development. Key qualities inherent in creative individuals, including mental flexibility, risk-taking, and self-motivation, and their role in cultural and professional development are discussed.

Keywords: psychology, creativity, culture, art psychology, artistic perception, creativity, personal development, interdisciplinary approach, creative thinking.

The connection between human psychology and culture is a fact that cannot be disputed. However, it is one thing to recognise its existence, and quite another to understand its nature, mechanisms and regularities. Specialists from the fields of cultural studies and psychology explore this relationship from different perspectives. Historically, their approaches have formed a unique division of tasks: culturalists focus on the features of thinking and behaviour that are shaped within a particular cultural environment, while psychologists focus on the study of universal aspects and laws of mental activity that are independent of cultural conditions. Within general psychology, cultural differences are often mentioned only as an aspect to be taken into account in order to create an objective and universal description of mental processes.

Psychology encompasses a variety of forms of human activity, and art occupies a special place in this spectrum. The psychology of art is a distinct field that investigates how people perceive and create artistic works. Its subject matter includes analysing the

personality traits that contribute to the perception and creation of art, as well as studying how these processes affect a person's life. Attention is paid to the personal characteristics of artists, the structure of their work, and the ways of perceiving works of literature, music, and other art forms.

The key problems facing this direction are three aspects: the peculiarities of the emotional and imaginative state of an individual when creating or perceiving aesthetic values, analysing the perception of art as a form of complicity in different periods of life, and the influence of art on a person's values, motivation and worldview.

Creativity is a process related to both the creation of cultural values and the transformation of personal ideas into cultural heritage. The works created become part of culture, gaining independence from their creator. These works, be they paintings, poems or scientific works, exist as independent objects, becoming the subject of analysis not only for psychology, but also for other sciences.

Psychology and art intersect in the study of human beings, but their approaches differ. Psychologists seek to objectively study mental processes, while artists emphasise the emotional and aesthetic side of human experience.

Art, according to specialists, becomes a social phenomenon when it contributes to the formation of personality, awakening new abilities, ideas and values in a person. However, the task of the psychologist is not to anticipate the social functions of art. His aim is to analyse the psychological mechanisms underlying artistic perception.

The study of creative processes allows psychologists to develop methods of personality formation. This is the potential of art psychology to achieve significant scientific results.

The main directions of research on this issue are presented in the article as follows:

The relationship between psychology and culture. Research on the relationship between psychology and culture is often associated with the study of the specifics of thinking and behaviour conditioned by the cultural environment. G. Hofstede[2] in his theory of cultural dimensions notes the influence of national and social values on personality behaviour. At the same time, representatives of general psychology, such as

L.S. Vygotsky[1], considered the role of culture in the formation of mental processes and higher human functions.

Art as an object of psychological study. The psychology of art was formed in the works of such researchers as L. Vygotsky [1], who emphasised the role of art in emotional development. In his book 'Psychology of Art' he states that the perception of an artwork is a complex emotional and intellectual process. Later studies in this field touched upon aspects of perception, empathy, and the influence of artistic works on the formation of value attitudes. The works of B. S. Meylakh [10] and M. Kaganov [8] confirm the interdisciplinary nature of the study of art.

Creativity as a key aspect of art psychology. Creativity is seen as a person's ability to go beyond stereotypical thinking. G. Guilford[3] introduced the concept of divergent thinking, emphasising its importance in the process of creativity. J. Ranko[9] and other modern researchers identify cognitive and personal characteristics that contribute to creative thinking: flexibility of mind, tolerance to uncertainty, self-motivation. The issues of diagnostics and assessment of creativity, such as the Torrance test[4], continue to be relevant in modern psychology.

Art as a factor of personality formation. The influence of art on personal development has been studied in detail in the works of M. Bakhtin[7] and A. Maslow[6]. Bakhtin emphasised the social nature of creativity and its ability to form ideals, values and worldview. Maslow[6] connected the perception of art with the need for self-realisation and aesthetic pleasure.

Methodological aspects of the study of art and psychology, the interdisciplinary nature of creativity research requires the use of integrated approaches. The works of modern authors, such as H. Gardner[5] ('Multiple Intelligences'), enrich the understanding of creativity mechanisms, emphasising the importance of integrating data from psychology, neurobiology, cultural studies and art.

Current Challenges and Research Perspectives.[12] To date, the study of art psychology faces a number of challenges, including:

The limitations of psychological methods in the study of artistic creative processes (Meilach)[10];

the need to integrate data from different disciplines to create more comprehensive models of creativity;

investigating the impact of digitalisation and modern technology on the perception of art.

At the same time, the prospects of research are connected with the development of neuroimaging technologies, which allow studying brain processes occurring during the perception and creation of works of art, as well as with the introduction of new educational programmes for the development of creative abilities.

Creativity is often perceived as something exceptional, accessible only to a select few, but it is a fundamental feature of human nature. Psychologists study creative thinking, highlighting its key qualities: the ability to find unconventional solutions, the ability to accept ambiguity, the willingness to take risks and objectively evaluate one's own work. These qualities form the image of an ideal innovator, although managing such people can be a challenge.

At the same time, creativity can be seen as a skill that everyone can develop. This understanding removes the halo of exclusivity and makes it more accessible. Creative thinking is opposed to traditional rationality because it breaks established stereotypes and offers new perspectives.

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In works of art, personality is manifested in the peculiarities of perception and emotional experiences of both the author and the characters. This aspect makes art texts a valuable material for psychological analysis, as they reflect unique manifestations of human nature.

Thus, creativity is regarded as an interdisciplinary object that requires an integrated approach. Psychology plays an important role in its study, but only in co-operation with other sciences it can reveal its essence.

Art and psychology, enriching each other, contribute to the expansion of knowledge about man and his capabilities.

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